

1 STK kinase addiction in pancreatic cancer.

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6 We describe signaling-based kinase addiction, likely developmental in origin and indicative of cellular
7 identity. We report here STK kinase addiction in pancreatic cancer. The specific STK kinases to which
8 kinase addiction in human PDAC was observed included Stk38, Stk24, and Stk26.

9 Citations

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